

The Shroud of Turin: The Static Loose Covering Model

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Abstract

The Shroud of Turin—a linen cloth bearing the frontal and dorsal images of a man and numerous bloodstains—is historically regarded by many as the burial shroud of Jesus of Nazareth. This study introduces the Static Loose Covering (SLC) model to define the physical context and body positioning present during image formation.

Our analysis suggests that purported anatomical anomalies within the Shroud image often arise from improper measurement techniques or misinterpretations of its three-dimensional properties. By examining high-definition photographs of both the recto (front) and verso (underside) of the Shroud, we show that the SLC model remains consistent with the physical evidence.

Rather than relying on algorithmic cloth simulations, this research utilizes photogrammetric scans of a human subject and actual draped cloth. For the first time in Shroud research, a precise mathematical formula was applied within a computer-based environment to generate the image based on these physical measurements. This methodology demonstrates that the Shroud image can form without the major distortions typically associated with a wrapped surface.

Furthermore, an investigation of the verso reveals blood images in areas previously categorized as bloodstains, adding a layer of complexity to any reproduction attempts. These data allow for a more precise determination of body positioning and highlight distinct behaviors between bloodstains located on skin versus hair. We conclude that the Shroud's intricate details, including the 3D correlation of bloodstains, are significantly more achievable using a human subject than a bas-relief sculpture. Finally, we address the inherent limitations of standard cloth simulations and present this as the first study to utilize verso-side photographic details to analyze the Shroud's image-formation mechanism.

Keywords: Shroud of Turin, Image Formation, Cloth Covering Model, Body-to-cloth Distance Encoding, Shroud Underside, Cluny Lirey Badge

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1. Introduction

The Shroud of Turin (hereafter ‘the Shroud’) is a rectangular linen textile measuring approximately 4.4 m in length by 1.1 m in width. It bears the faint frontal and dorsal images of a nude male exhibiting trauma consistent with the New Testament accounts of the passion of Jesus of Nazareth. These include marks indicative of severe flagellation, a circumferential crowning with thorns, crucifixion, and a post-mortem piercing of the right thorax (Figure 1A). Specifically, the man on the Shroud displays over one hundred scourge marks distributed across the torso and limbs, as well as distinct

wounds to the wrists and feet consistent with Roman crucifixion practices.

Historical records indicate that the Shroud was exhibited around 1357 and in 1389 at the collegiate church of Lirey, France, founded by the knight Geoffroy de Charny. In 1453, his granddaughter, Marguerite de Charny, ceded the textile to Duke Louis I of Savoy. In 1502, Duke Charles III relocated the Shroud to the Sainte-Chapelle of Chambéry. This prestigious designation, modeled after the original foundation by Saint Louis in Paris, was reserved for palatine chapels that housed a relic of Christ and belonged to a descendant of the French royal line. Such foundations typically required Papal recognition to confirm their unique status and liturgical independence.

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In 1532, a catastrophic fire at the Sainte-Chapelle in Chambéry substantially damaged the Shroud. The intensity of the heat caused the silver reliquary to melt, resulting in symmetrical burn holes that flank the central image and partially obscure the upper arm and shoulder regions. In 1578, Duke Emmanuel Philibert of Savoy transferred the Shroud to the Cathedral of Turin, the new capital of the Duchy of Savoy since 1563. Beginning in 1694, the Shroud was housed in a dedicated chapel designed by the architect Guarino Guarini, a structural masterpiece connected to both the Cathedral and the Royal Palace (Scott (2003, 1995)).

The Shroud mainly remained in this location until April 11, 1997, when a major fire severely damaged the Guarini chapel, necessitating a rescue of the relic and its subsequent relocation to a climate-controlled conservation facility within the Cathedral. The Shroud is displayed only during special expositions, such as the 2015 event honoring the 200th anniversary of Saint John Bosco's birth.

In 2002, the Shroud underwent a major restoration: fire-damaged patches from 1532 were removed and the 1534 backing cloth was replaced. This enabled high-definition photography of both the recto (front) and, for the first time, the verso (underside) sides. The recto shows the double-image; the verso has no image (Figure 1A and B) but bloodstains that seeped through from the recto. Both photographs are used in this work. Figure 1C shows the recto negative, which better reveals faint images of blood that are difficult to see in the positive photograph, such as those on the arms (Section 3.2).

The Shroud appears as a real shroud: its apparent bloodstains have yellow halos consistent with blood plasma, and photomicrographs show blood particles rather than paint (Figure 2 A, B and C). Paint cannot replicate such details. These apparent bloodstains have tested positive for blood (Jumper et al. (1984)). Given these physical and chemical characteristics, they are hereafter called bloodstains.

The image on the Shroud presents a profound forensic problem: under normal conditions, a corpse does not leave a detailed, high-resolution imprint on its burial shroud. No other historical or archaeological instance of such an image is known to exist. Consequently, the Shroud remains a unique phenomenon in forensic science and history, defying conventional naturalistic explanations of image formation.

The entire image (frontal and dorsal) consists of a yellowing restricted to the primary cell walls of the top-most fibrils of the linen threads (Pellicori (2025)). This extreme superficiality is a unique characteristic that distinguishes the Shroud from any known artistic technique

across all historical periods. The image is uniformly pale and lacks any detectable binding medium or pigment, even under high-power magnification. As shown in Figure 1D and E (and further supported by the 1978 STURP microphotographs (Latendresse (2010, 2026))), the image resulted from the dehydration and conjugation of the flax cellulose itself, though the specific energy source for this chemical change remains unidentified (Jumper et al. (1984)).

While the bloodstains largely correlate with direct contact between the textile and a corpse, the body image itself contradicts a simple contact mechanism. If the image were formed by physical contact alone, the flattening of the cloth would produce significant lateral “wraparound” distortions—most notably in the facial region—which are absent in the Shroud's orthographic-like projection.

The Shroud exhibits precise anatomical registration between the bloodstains and the body image. Direct alignment at the wrists, forehead, and feet precludes significant movement during the transition from blood transfer to image formation; even a 1 cm vertical or horizontal displacement would be detectable. This spatial consistency provides the empirical foundation for the Static Loose Covering (SLC) model (Section 2).

Section 3 presents other important properties: matching the image with realistic bloodstains coherent with hair and body three-dimensionality. These two subtle and distinct properties have been ignored in all reproduction attempts. They can be detected using the Shroud's verso side. These observations further support the SLC model.

While some researchers allege anatomical anomalies, such claims often stem from misinterpretations of the 3D-to-2D projection or measurement errors (Section 4).

Furthermore, critics often argue that any cloth projection must yield distortions. For instance, Cicero Moraes (2025) used computer-based simulations to demonstrate distortions from a specific draping configuration. However, this approach is logically flawed: the relevant inquiry is not whether arbitrary coverings distort, but whether a natural configuration exists that does not. Section 5 demonstrates that the SLC model provides such a configuration, while Section 6 addresses the technical limitations of Moraes simulations.

While some historical perspectives suggest otherwise, the question of whether the Shroud can be reproduced is central to establishing its origin. Based on the evidence from historical copies and recent experimental studies, Section 7 offers a succinct discussion on reproducibility, particularly regarding the use of a bas-relief.

We do not address the chemical or physical mecha-

nism that produced the Shroud's image. However, we assume this mechanism operated at short distance (a few centimeters, as in the SLC model), explaining the absence of images from the body's sides and head top. Our emphasis is on the frontal image; the dorsal image requires a separate analysis deferred to future study.

2. The Static Loose Covering Model

The Static Loose Covering (SLC) foundational model assumes the frontal part of the Shroud was loosely covering a real body forming a 'tent' like cover touching the upper part of the body. That can be done by tensioning the cloth by two or three individuals and lowered onto a supine body resting on a flat surface (Figure 3). This "top-down" draping establishes the initial contact points for blood transfer and defines the subsequent image-formation geometry.

The subject is modeled in an essentially straight position; while a slight left-knee elevation is noted, significant knee flexion—such as the "isosceles triangle" posture proposed by Bevilacqua (2018)—is rejected. Such flexion would preclude the observed dorsal leg bloodstains unless a complex cloth contouring is assumed. A straight posture maintains coherent length measurements between the frontal and dorsal images (Figure 6).

Asymmetry in the foot region—a full plantar image and bloodstain for the right foot versus a partial heel stain for the left—suggests the left foot was positioned over the right. This created an uneven frontal surface and likely explains the nail-wound bloodstain lacking a corresponding pedal image. Rare peripheral stains (e.g., near the elbow or foot) likely resulted from blood droplets or contact during the initial positioning of the body.

The model posits that the Shroud remained stationary after initial contact. Most bloodstains resulted from direct contact, while most of the body image formed via a short-range (around 10 cm) vertical projection. Image intensity is modeled as an inverse function of the body-to-cloth distance. The absence of lateral limb images and the lack of "wraparound" distortion confirm a loose, non-contouring drape.

The SLC model provides a testable framework for image formation where the textile acts as a static, proximity-sensitive recorder. This foundational model can be validated through physical reconstructions, 3D scanning (Section 5), or high-fidelity computer simulations.

2.1. The Three-dimensionality of the Image

The Shroud image encodes three-dimensional data via a distance-dependent mechanism: cellulose oxidation intensity is inversely proportional to the cloth-to-body distance. In the SLC model, this 3D encoding is "shallow" because the textile conforms to the body's topography rather than remaining a flat plane. This geometry explains the "standing" appearance of the hair; the cloth naturally drapes closer to the hair on the sides of the face, also creating the lateral gaps (Figure 4A).

The 3D nature of the image was understood quite early once it was closely analyzed by an artist. The 14th-century artist of the Cluny badge demonstrated this understanding by meticulously embossing asymmetrical dorsal arm details that align with the frontal view (Figure 5C) and other details such as the feet. It becomes clear from the first photograph of the Shroud by Secondo Pia in 1898. Paul Vignon described the "law of distances" as early as 1902, noting it was "manifest in the impressions on the Shroud" (Vignon, 1902, p. 162).

The Shroud's "photographic negativity" is not a separate mechanism but a direct byproduct of the distance-to-color encoding. While the negative appears more realistic to the human eye, it is simply a visual effect of the primary spatial recording; there is only one underlying mechanism involved.

While spatial encoding can be manually painted, the Shroud remains the first historical instance of such a feature. Traditional art relies on perspective, shading, and texture to simulate depth—techniques directly perceivable to the human eye, which is fundamentally different from the Shroud's encoding. A notable example of such artistic illusion is the trompe-l'oeil ceiling of the Sainte-Chapelle in Chambéry, where shading creates a false 3D appearance of stone ornaments.

Finally, the bloodstains themselves record the 3D topography of the body (Section 3). This property is frequently overlooked in reproduction attempts and presents a significant challenge to the hypothesis that a bas-relief was used to create the image.

3. Blood Transfer from a Real Body

A fundamental tenet of the SLC model is that the Shroud's position remained fixed from the initial contact for blood transfer through the final stage of image formation. In this section we show that this constraint is empirically supported by the precise co-registration of bloodstains and body features. For instance, bloodstains mediated by the hair and those following the 3D topography of the limbs align perfectly with the underlying image. Any successful reproduction must satisfy

this “static” requirement; achieving such spatial precision is practically feasible only if the textile remains stationary, rather than being subjected to a two-stage process involving cloth movement or repositioning between events.

3.1. Bloodstains Over Hair

The head area (Figure 4A) features bloodstains labeled R_n ($1 \leq n \leq 9$), with their corresponding verso counterparts (V_n) shown in Figure 4B. Stains R_1 – R_3 are located on the skin of the forehead, while R_4 – R_9 are located on the hair. A distinct correlation exists between the volume of blood that seeped through the textile and the nature of the underlying surface: blood on the smooth surface of the skin seeped abundantly, whereas blood on the hair did not. This is attributed to the hair’s porous structure, which absorbs and traps blood, preventing the saturation required to penetrate to the verso.

Comparative analysis of adjacent stains clarifies this relationship. R_1 (skin) and R_4 (eyebrow) provide a clear contrast; V_1 is prominent on the verso, while V_4 is barely detectable. Similarly, R_3 (skin) and R_5 (hair-line) are physically adjacent and connected, yet V_3 is clearly visible while V_5 is nearly absent. For the remaining stains on the hair (R_6 – R_9), the verso counterparts (V_6 – V_9) are either barely visible or nonexistent.

These findings reinforce the static nature of the Shroud. The fact that adjacent, connected stains (R_3 and R_5) exhibit completely different seepage patterns based on the underlying anatomy proves that the cloth remained perfectly stationary. This evidence effectively invalidates the “moving cloth” hypothesis presented by Lavoie (2023, 2002), as any movement between blood transfer and image formation would have decoupled these stains from their specific anatomical boundaries (Section 3.3).

3.2. Bloodstains vs. Blood Images

A subtle but vital distinction exists between physical bloodstains and “images of blood.” A *bloodstain* is the result of direct contact, where blood on the body was physically transferred to the linen fibers, leaving particulate matter. These stains are visible as distinct, reddish-brown features on the recto side (Figures 2 and 4).

However, observations suggest that blood on the body located a few millimeters away from the cloth may have produced an *image of blood* through the same proximity-dependent mechanism that formed the body image. In these instances, no blood particles exist on the

Shroud; rather, the cloth features a straw-yellow oxidation identical in nature to the skin image but of higher intensity. On a large-scale photograph, these images are often indistinguishable from true bloodstains, yet they provide essential evidence of the subject’s three-dimensionality.

The 2002 verso photograph provides a definitive method for differentiation. Since the body image does not penetrate the cloth, it is absent from the verso. Consequently, any blood-colored feature visible on the underside is a confirmed *bloodstain* that seeped through the weave. If an apparent wound is intense on the recto but entirely absent on the verso, it can be identified as an image of blood rather than a stain. While this possibility was previously discussed by John Jackson (1987), the availability of the verso imagery allows for a more rigorous identification. In the following sections, we analyze these images of blood and wounds to demonstrate their coherence with a 3D body and the SLC model.

Figure 4 provides a forensic comparison of the right forearm between the recto (Figure 4A) and verso (Figure 4B) views. The large bloodstain labeled R_1 seeped through the textile, producing the corresponding V_1 on the verso side and confirming direct contact.

In contrast, the bloodstain R_2 transitions into an “image of blood” as it nears the lateral edge. This transition is also evident in the two pale features labeled R_3 ; the corresponding verso locations (V_3) show no detectable blood, confirming that these recto features are proximity-based images rather than physical stains. This spatial distribution is entirely coherent with the three-dimensionality of the forearm, where the rounded edges of the limb lose contact with the Shroud but remain within the effective distance for image formation. Similar observations apply to the left forearm.

3.3. Supposed Misalignment of Bloodstains

Gilbert Lavoie (2023; 2002), alongside Giulio Fanti and Emanuela Marinelli (2001), proposes a two-step process where the Shroud was initially wrapped tightly around the head to transfer blood from the cheeks, then flattened to record the frontal image. This flattening supposedly explains why blood appears over the hair.

This hypothesis is fundamentally flawed as it ignores the global consequences of such a transition; flattening a wrapped cloth would cause massive vertical and horizontal misalignments across all other bloodstains. Furthermore, there is no forensic necessity to assume the blood originated on the cheeks; blood could naturally drip from the scalp into the hair, as observed in the stains above the forehead and the dorsal head image (Section 3.1).

Similarly, John Jackson’s (1990) *Cloth Collapse Hypothesis* posits that the image formed as the textile collapsed through a disappearing body. This model attempts to resolve the same perceived misalignments and the lack of lateral imaging. However, a collapsing textile would inevitably buckle and fold, introducing severe geometric distortions. These “issues” are nonexistent in the SLC model, which accounts for the lack of lateral images through a natural, static drape without the need for complex cloth movement.

4. Claims of Anatomical Anomalies

The Static Loose Covering (SLC) model provides the necessary framework for interpreting anatomical dimensions. Precise boundary determination is complicated by historical water stains, fire damage, and potential textile stretching over centuries (Latendresse (2005)). These factors necessitate a case-by-case analysis of each measurement rather than a generalized rejection of the image’s anatomical validity.

Many claims of anatomical “impossibility” rely on vague visual assessments or a failure to account for the 3D-to-2D projection. For instance, Elio Quiroga Rodriguez (2024) cites the hand placement over the genitals as an inconsistency suggesting “artistic intervention.” Notably, Rodriguez’s analysis begins with a basic lack of familiarity with the established literature, confusing the anatomical left and right of the subject—an orientation confirmed by the thoracic bloodstain.

Rodriguez claims that the right arm is 7–10 cm longer than the left, proposing the following:

“To confirm this, a straightforward experiment can be conducted: Measure the height of the figure in a photograph of the Holy Shroud and add the length of the arms. If the resulting measurement exceeds the height of an average human adult, it raises reasonable doubt regarding whether the image accurately represents an adult with typical proportions.”

This “straightforward experiment” is conceptually confusing, as measuring the arms independently would suffice to test the claim. Surprisingly, Rodriguez fails to present any actual measurements. Instead, he relies on skeletal overlays on photographs that suffer from two fundamental errors: ignoring the partially visible bent fingers of the left hand, which significantly alters the perceived length of the limb; ignoring the apparent retraction of the left forearm away from the torso.

In Figure 5A, we map the anatomical landmarks and measurements directly on the image. Red lines denote the forearms and hands, while blue arrows identify the knuckles (metacarpal-phalangeal joints), the left wrist, and the olecranon processes (elbows). Dotted blue lines indicate the projected paths of the forearms inferred from the visible bloodstains and the asymmetrical retraction of the left arm. Measurements were obtained by using the Shroud Scope (Latendresse (2010)).

Our analysis of the hand morphology reveals that the left-hand fingers are bent at the proximal-middle phalangeal joints. While the right hand is only partially resolved, its knuckles remain identifiable.

The right arm serves as the primary anatomical reference due to the clarity of its distal features. We directly measure the longest right-hand finger (FiR) at 11.8 cm and the forearm-plus-hand (FHR, knuckle to olecranon) at approximately 41 cm. Summed, these provide a total length of 52.8 cm, closely aligning with the 53.7 ± 2.7 cm reported by Ercoline *et al.* (1982).

The left forearm is retracted dorsally and laterally compared to the right, a position evidenced by the increased void between the arm and the torso and the off-center location of the left wrist, both visible on the Shroud frontal image. This 3D orientation is supported by the 14th-century Cluny pilgrim badge (Figure 5C), which correctly depicts the left arm as more protruding outward, as given from the frontal depiction, and toward the dorsal surface as given from the more 3D protruding upper arm on the dorsal depiction. The inclusion of such a subtle anatomical feature is highly plausible given the craftsman’s meticulous attention to detail; the mold also accurately represents the textile’s herringbone weave, the disappearance of the feet on the frontal image, and the presence of two distinct feet on the dorsal image, complete and partial.

Because the left elbow is obscured by a burn hole, we adopt the right-arm measurements (FiR and FHR) as proxies. In a 2D photograph, the left arm’s vector appears to move “up,” but within the SLC model’s 3D projection, this signifies a downward and lateral path toward the dorsal cloth. This interpretation places the left elbow where the anatomy of the forearm would naturally terminate beneath the existing hole.

The “seven to ten centimeter” discrepancy claimed by critics such as Rodriguez (2024) vanishes when two factors are accounted for: the omission of the bent portion of the left fingers (approx. 6 cm); the added length required for the retracted left arm.

Similar claims by Louis Cador (2021) identify a “shortening” of the left arm by placing the elbow at a water-stain boundary. However, this contradicts the

anatomical direction of the forearm and confuses the water stain as being part of the image.

Thierry Castex (2010) claims the Shroud’s legs are substantially too long based on perceived disproportions between the legs and torso. However, this claim lacks empirical measurements and relies on a modified image generated through an unspecified methodology. To justify this view, Castex proposes an anatomical reinterpretation: removing the perceived buttocks from the dorsal image and reclassifying the upper thighs as buttocks—effectively suggesting a duplication of these features on the Shroud.

In Figure 5B, we report three primary dorsal measurements using specific anatomical landmarks:

- **Head-Neck (HND, 25 cm):** From the vertex (top of the head) to the C7 vertebra.
- **Torso (TD, 69 cm):** From the C7 vertebra to the hip joint.
- **Legs (LD, 94 cm):** From the hip joint to the heel.

These values yield a total height of 188 cm. The resulting proportions—50% for the legs, 36.7% for the torso, and 13.3% for the head—align well with the anatomical standards published by Bogin *et al.* (2010) and Alberti *et al.* (2022). Contrary to visual impressions of disproportion, these measurements confirm that the limb lengths are anatomically coherent.

The 188 cm height estimate is uncertain because it assumes the fabric’s dimensions have remained static. However, decades of being rolled and the stress of vertical displays likely caused stretching. Nicola Scarpelli (1983) confirmed this through an analysis of weaving deformation; although his estimate may be extreme, any such lengthening would reduce the man’s calculated height.

In summary, current claims of anatomical disproportions in the Shroud image consistently lack rigorous empirical analysis. The SLC model demonstrates that perceived anomalies are often artifacts of the 3D-to-2D projection and the natural drape of the textile. At a minimum, any challenge to the anatomical validity of the image must be supported by direct measurements, clearly defined anatomical landmarks, and an objective interpretive methodology. Vague visual assessments, absent precise measurements and ignoring the image-formation geometry, are scientifically unconvincing.

5. A Real Cloth on a Real Body

In this section, we demonstrate, among other findings, that a natural covering of a cloth on a real body,

coherent with the SLC model, does not create major image distortions under vertical projection, given contact points corresponding to bloodstain locations on the Shroud.

We used photogrammetry using an iPhone 15 (Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA, USA) and the application ScaniVerse (Niantic, Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA) to capture 3D scans of a human subject in supine position, partially replicating the posture of the figure on the Shroud (Figure 6A). The legs were positioned flat against the horizontal support to ensure that bloodstains from the calves and thighs would be visible on the dorsal image, as observed on the Shroud. The forearms and hands were positioned to match the Shroud configuration, allowing the cloth covering the ventral surface to contact them. The left upper arm was positioned slightly farther from the thorax than the right, consistent with the asymmetry observed on the Shroud. Although photogrammetry produced relatively low-resolution scans—evident in surface irregularities and missing mesh faces on the left upper arm—the quality is sufficient for the present analysis.

A second scan was performed with the subject covered by a linen cloth of the same dimensions as the Shroud (Figure 6B). The cloth made contact with the nose, forehead, forearms, thorax, left hand, legs, and knees. Consistent with the SLC model, the cloth did not contact the lateral aspects of the body.

These two 3D scans were independently imported as meshes into the Blender software Blender Online Community (2025) to simulate the image formation process by projecting the body’s surface onto the cloth. Alignment of the body mesh with the cloth mesh was achieved through minor rotations and translations to preserve the original scan configuration. Measurements on the subject mesh confirmed a height of approximately 170 cm. The image generation script automatically verified that portions of the cloth mesh were in contact with the subject mesh.

The color intensity i of a vertex of the mesh cloth is governed by the formula

$$i = 1 - \left(\frac{d}{m}\right)^p$$

where d is the vertical distance between the body and the vertex, m is the maximum distance considered, and $p > 0$ is a constant. We experimented with several values for p and found $p = \frac{1}{2}$ (the square root), as implemented in the Blender script, produces images most coherent with the Shroud. For example, the linear case ($p = 1$) generates intense colors unlike those observed

on the Shroud (see Figure 6, panel G). Note that i is inversely related to the distance d , consistent with the Shroud image. Furthermore, $0 \leq \frac{d}{m} \leq 1$, which implies that $0 \leq i \leq 1$ for any $p > 0$, ensuring the formula is well-behaved across all parameters.

In Blender, the projection is implemented via a script with two parameters: depth d , which defines the cut-off range for distances considered, and power p , which determines color intensity according to the formula above. When d is not specified, the script uses the maximum depth detected.

Following the initial image formation on the draped cloth, a second script executes a geometric flattening of the mesh. The image undergoes this transformation, ensuring that the resulting 2D representation accurately reflects how a potentially distorted draped image would appear once the cloth is laid flat. This is an essential step, performed with high geometric precision to ensure the validity of the resulting 2D projection

The transition from a 3D draped model to a 2D planar image was achieved through an area-preserving flattening algorithm implemented using the Blender Python API. The process uses an Angle-Based Flattening (ABF) unwrapping method to minimize angular distortion of the mesh polygons. To maintain the physical textile dimensions, the script calculates the total 3D surface area (A_{3D}) of the draped cloth and compares it to the initial 2D area (A_{2D}) after unwrapping. A uniform scaling factor $s = \sqrt{A_{3D}/A_{2D}}$ was then applied to the planar coordinates to ensure that the final 2D representation matched the original 3D surface area. This step is essential for preserving the aspect ratio and ensuring that the projected image intensity distributions are mapped accurately onto the flat surface. An internal numerical validation confirms that the precision error between the target 3D area and the final 2D area was negligible (typically $|A_{3D} - A_{final}| < 10^{-6}$).

As shown in Figure 6 panels C, D and E, the formula successfully generates simulated images in draped, flattened and inverted states. The simulation yields a high degree of anatomical fidelity, with the facial features, ears, left hand, right-hand digits, and knees all remaining clearly discernible in the flattened image. Most notably, the images exhibit a small geometric distortion. A slight enlargement of the body is observed, particularly in the region of the left calf—a characteristic also discernible on the Shroud.

Quantitatively, at the widest point of the image (at the level of the nipples), the image width increased from approximately 49.0 cm to 53.3 cm ($\delta = 4.3$ cm) while total body height increased from 170.2 cm to 176.3 cm ($\delta = 6.1$ cm). The ratio of the original body height

to width is 3.47, compared to a flattened ratio of 3.30. These close ratios confirm that this flattening process operates at near-uniform scaling, maintaining anatomical proportions with a variance of approximately 5%.

Furthermore, the Shroud exhibits a notable discrepancy between the dorsal image (approximately 188 cm) and the longer frontal image (approximately 196 cm). Within the SLC model, the dorsal side of the subject lies flat against the cloth, meaning the dorsal image length remains nearly identical to the subject's actual 3D height. In contrast, the frontal image must accommodate the subject's anatomical contours. In our experiment, this process resulted in a frontal length of 176.3 cm compared to a dorsal height of 170.2 cm—a difference of 6.1 cm. The ratio of frontal-to-dorsal length for the Shroud is 1.042, which closely aligns with the 1.035 ratio produced by our experiment. Consequently, the SLC model provides a robust geometric explanation for the greater length of the frontal image relative to the dorsal image.

Other examples of generated images are shown in panels F, G and H. For F, a specific maximum distance of 8 cm is used, which eliminates some features such as the ears. For G, a linear formula is used ($p = 1.0$), which increases the darkness of the image. As can be observed when comparing images H and E, that reduces the 3D characteristics of the image, in particular for the regions where the cloth is in near contact with the body such as arms, torso and thighs.

The specific mathematical function governing intensity is not critical to this model, as alternative functions can produce comparable results. Because the absence of major distortion arises from the spatial relationship between the body and the draped cloth, the core findings remain robust regardless of the intensity formula chosen. Producing images with greater fidelity to the Shroud will require further investigation of appropriate formulae and potentially other properties such as diffusion effects. It may require a simulation of image generation at the level of the threads, which is beyond the scope of the present study.

While the anatomical detail of the simulated image—particularly the face—is less pronounced than that observed on the Shroud, achieving high-fidelity anatomical reproduction was not the primary objective of this study. Rather, this research demonstrates the absence of significant image distortions when applying the SLC model to a naturally draped cloth over a human body.

See the Data Availability Statement Section for access to the meshes and scripts used to produce the images presented in this section.

6. Computer Simulation of Textiles

Cicero Moraes (2025) recently utilized computer simulations of textiles to argue that a 3D body covering inevitably generates major image distortions. However, demonstrating that a single, specific covering configuration fails does not preclude the existence of a configuration that succeeds—such as one conforming to the SLC model.

The primary limitation of the Moraes model is that the body is modeled “floating” without a supporting surface (Figure 6A in Moraes (2025)). In a natural entombment scenario, a rigid platform of sufficient width allows the cloth to drape and rest on the surface adjacent to the body. Without this support, the simulated cloth hangs vertically, making excessive contact with the lateral limbs and hair. In the SLC model, the platform ensures the cloth “tents” over the body, maintaining contact with frontal prominences while avoiding the lateral wraparound that causes image distortions.

Moraes further proposes a bas-relief solution, but the resulting simulation produces a flat appearance lacking the varied intensity characteristic of the Shroud (Figure 6C in Moraes (2025)). Furthermore, the model used is not a true bas-relief, as it features only a single relief level, failing to account for the depth-dependent spatial encoding observed on the Shroud.

These simulations far disprove the possibility of a 3D body covering; rather, they highlight the necessity of accurate physical modeling—including a supporting platform—to replicate the Shroud’s unique image characteristics. In fact, the SLC creates a proper image without major distortions disproving the result of Moraes.

Furthermore, computer-aided cloth modeling is highly dependent on parameters such as textile flexibility, surface friction, and textile tension. Unless it is clearly demonstrated that they correspond to a linen cloth, any such simulation remains doubtful.

7. Reproducibility of the Shroud

Historically, authenticity was often predicated on provenance and ecclesiastical certification, but today it has moved into scientific domains such as chemistry, physics, forensics and history. Since the 16th century, numerous artistic copies have been produced, yet as Luigi Fossati (1984a; 1984b) and Andrew Casper (2021) demonstrate, even the most talented artists failed to replicate the Shroud’s subtleties. Unlike master-painting forgeries, no historical or modern

attempt has successfully mimicked the original’s characteristics, underscoring the profound difficulty of the task.

Modern researchers have attempted to replicate the Shroud through various means, including proto-photography and chemical processes (Garlaschelli (2010); McCrone (1999); Allen (2017); Craig and Breesee (1994)). However, these attempts fail to satisfy two primary forensic criteria. First, they lack the specific fibril-level characteristics (e.g., cellulose oxidation) observed in photomicrographs—data that these studies often omit entirely. Second, they fail to address the static co-registration of bloodstains with the body image.

Furthermore, claims attributing the Shroud to a specific medieval artist remain totally elusive. The few proposed cases remain largely unproven. For example, Paolo Antinucci (2022) proposed the Italian artist Cenni di Pepo, known as Cimabue (died 1302). It is untenable because Cimabue never produced any painting closely related to the Shroud. And if we were to believe Bishop Pierre d’Arcis, the alleged artist confessed to Henri de Poitiers, who became bishop of Troyes five decades after Cimabue’s death.

To date, no art historian has provided any evidence of a medieval artist capable of producing such a unique spatial and microscopic record.

7.1. Bas-relief versus Real Body

It has been proposed by several researchers that the Shroud with its image could have been produced by a solid bas-relief. The primary reason to use a bas-relief is to produce an image by contact and still produce a three-dimensional image without major distortions. Such is the approach of Luigi Garlaschelli (2010) for the face. However, the results are far from compelling, and its author admits that more work is needed.

Another example is the bas-relief presentation by the popular scientific magazine *Science et Vie* (Bourdial (2005)) successfully producing a coarse 3D-like effect, but this is a trivial achievement. The Shroud’s uniqueness lies in the accuracy of its gradual spatial encoding, a feature missing from the “dabbing” techniques of bas-relief attempts, which produce coarse, non-microscopic results.

However, we have shown that a real body can produce all the details regarding the three-dimensionality and coherent with the bloodstains behavior as seen on the Shroud without major image distortion. The use of a bas-relief complicates the production of these details, because different hardness would need to be used (such as hair), and bloodstains and image of bloodstains

would need to be produced separately with a very precise alignment. This last step has never even been attempted with a bas-relief.

8. Conclusion

Empirical measurements of high-definition photographs substantiate the anatomical integrity of the man of the Shroud. The alleged anatomical anomalies of the Shroud image, as proposed by several authors, are found to be analytically invalid. These claims typically rely on visual impressions rather than empirical data; where measurements are provided, they frequently stem from a misinterpretation of the image geometry, or a failure to account for the 3D projection of a real human subject.

The behavior of bloodstains across different surfaces—specifically hair and skin—is entirely consistent with a real body. This forensic co-registration demonstrates that the Shroud must have remained stationary from the moment of blood transfer through the formation of the image. Analysis of the verso side further confirms the complexity of this process, identifying blood images instead of bloodstains. The presence of both bloodstains and blood images suggests a level of forensic subtlety that transcends any existing reproduction attempts.

The **Static Loose Covering (SLC)** model is uniquely coherent with these observations. By accounting for a supported body and a natural, non-contouring drape, the model explains the absence of the major image distortions that plague other 3D theories. While computer cloth simulations offer a modern tool for study, they are highly sensitive to parameters such as textile weight, internal tension, stiffness, and friction. Consequently, physical 3D scanning of a real cloth and body provides more accurate data than simulations based on unsubstantiated parameters.

Ultimately, the image and bloodstains of the Shroud are most parsimoniously explained by contact with a real human body rather than a sculpted bas-relief. The requirement to reproduce 3D blood transfer across heterogeneous surfaces while maintaining perfect spatial alignment with the resulting image remains an unmet challenge for the bas-relief hypothesis.

Looking ahead, future studies should utilize a higher-precision 3D scanner to obtain clearer representations of the body and the cloth. While the current formula used to project the body onto the fabric does not fully capture the fine anatomical details visible on the Shroud, it is important to note that a perfect image replication was not the primary objective of this study. Instead,

our goal was to demonstrate that the SLC model produces no major image distortions and remains coherent with the known characteristics of the bloodstains. Further research will refine the projection algorithm using higher-quality scans to build upon this foundational consistency.

Data Availability Statement

The recto and verso images of the Shroud, the scan meshes of the human subject and cloth, the Blender Python script to generate images and the images of Figure 6 are available on Figshare at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.31083784>. The script supports any meshes of human subject and cloth, and the provided meshes can be used to produce different images by varying the parameters of the script.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the author used Claude Sonnet 4.5 (Anthropic) in order to improve the readability of the text and to assist in developing the Blender visualization script. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Figure 1: The Shroud's Recto and Verso Surfaces. **A:** Full-length photograph of the Shroud's recto (front) surface, displaying both the frontal and dorsal body images and associated bloodstains. (Courtesy of Gian Carlo Durante, 2002). **B:** Photograph of the verso (underside) surface. (Courtesy of Gian Carlo Durante, 2002). Note the total absence of a body image, while the bloodstains remain visible due to seepage from the recto side. **C:** A color-inverted (negative) rendering of photograph A. *Note: All images are oriented such that the right side of the anatomical body corresponds to the right side of the photograph.*

Figure 2: Microscopic and Morphological Characteristics of the Shroud Image. **A:** 200× photomicrograph of a bloodstain region captured during the 2002 restoration. (Courtesy of Karlheinz Dietz). The particulate morphology of the bloodstain (ME-06, from the Collection of Mark Evans) suggests the absence of a binding medium or paint-like application. **B:** 32× photomicrograph of a bloodstain from the dorsal lumbar region (small of the back). (Courtesy of Mark Evans and Barrie Schwartz, 1978). **C:** 64× photomicrograph (ME-29) of the nasal region. Note the highly superficial coloration of the threads limited to the top flax fibrils. **D:** 32× photomicrograph (ME-15) of a non-image control area, illustrating the baseline state of the linen fibers. **E:** Color-enhanced photograph of a major bloodstain from the right foot. A distinct serum halo, indicative of blood plasma, is visible surrounding the central red clot. (Courtesy of Karlheinz Dietz, 2002).

A

B

Figure 3: Seventeenth-century Iconographic Depictions of the Shroud. **A:** A large-scale oil painting (1660) by Gio-Gasparo Baldoino (also known as Jean-Gaspard Baudoin, 1590–1669), located in the *Chapelle de la Très-Sainte-Trinité et du Saint-Suaire* in Nice, France. The composition features two registers: the celestial upper register depicts angels displaying the Shroud, while the lower register shows the entombment of Jesus with the textile held taut across the body. Public domain. **B:** A smaller work by Giovanni Battista della Rovere (1560–1627), known as “Il Fiammenghino” (Turin). Similar to the Baldoino piece, it utilizes a dual-register format; the lower portion depicts the Shroud maintained in a taut configuration over the body at the foot of the cross. Public domain. *Note: These paintings show a natural way to position the Shroud as a Static Loose Covering (SLC) detailed in Section 2.*

A

B

C

D

Figure 4: Macro photographs of blood features on head and right arm (recto and verso). **A**: the recto image of the head with the main bloodstains; **B**: the corresponding verso of the head with bloodstains; **C**: the recto image of the right forearm; **D**: the corresponding verso of the right forearm.

Figure 5: Length measurements of frontal arms and whole dorsal body. **A:** the frontal image with measurements of forearms and fingers; **B:** the dorsal images with measurements of body height, length of legs, torso and head; **C:** the Shroud depicted on the Cluny Lirey badge showing a complete left arm more retracted towards the outside and back than the right arm. (Mario Latendresse, 2022). Note: that badge was made in the second-half of the 14th century before the fire of 1532 that damage the image of both upper arms. Note: Due to the interplay of light and shadow, the figure may appear concave, though it is a solid convex relief.

Figure 6: Simulated images from cloth draped over a human subject. **A**: 3D scan of a 170 cm tall human subject. **B**: 3D scan of the same subject in supine position, covered by a linen cloth. **C**: Image produced by vertical projection with maximum depth and $p = 0.5$, with cloth still covering the subject. **D**: Image C after algorithmic flattening. **E**: Negative of image D. **F**: Image produced with parameters $d = 8$ cm and $p = 0.5$, after flattening. **G**: Image produced with maximum depth and $p = 1.0$, after flattening. **H**: Negative of image G. Note: All images were extracted from the Blender 3D viewport. Anatomical left corresponds to the left side of each image. All images are available at higher precision as supplementary materials (see the Data Availability Statement Section).